

10-minute unguided exposure – open-loop tracking is good to a fraction of an arcsecond over the time interval.
 Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/C. Briceño

SOAR Renewal Program

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It has been more than 20 years since the start of construction at the Southern Astrophysical Research (SOAR) Telescope, and not surprisingly, many of the subsystems in the telescope and dome have started to show their age. Similar concerns apply to the scientific instruments as well. Starting a decade ago, SOAR began a program of renewing obsolete subsystems, with a focus on electronics and software. SOAR users are doubtless aware of the instrumentation projects at the telescope, but the scope of the overall effort extends to the telescope and facilities in general.

Instrumentation

Regular users of SOAR will be familiar with the instrumentation suite, but a brief overview will help supply perspective. In some cases, new instruments are part of the original development plan, while in others they are replacing older capabilities.

The following two instruments represent the final deliveries of the initial instrument suite for SOAR:

- **SOAR Integral Field Spectrograph (SIFS).** The SOAR IFU spectrograph was finally commissioned at SOAR in early 2017, with science verification during both the

2017A and B semesters. Since then it has seen regular use by the Brazilian community, with less frequent use by observers from other SOAR partners. The instrument capabilities are described on the [NOIRLab Science website](#); the original design paper is Lepine et al. (2003).

- **STELLES.** The SOAR Echelle Spectrograph is currently undergoing final integration at SOAR, including limited on-sky testing by early CY 2024. This work was delayed by multiple factors, including the COVID-19 pandemic. The original design paper is Castilho et al. (2004).

Two additional instruments are replacing older capabilities:

- **TripleSpec 4.1** is a version of the original TripleSpec IR spectrograph that was originally built for the Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope and subsequently adapted for use at SOAR. It replaced the OSIRIS IR spectrograph, which was decommissioned in 2015 after major failures. Instrument information for users is also provided on the [NOIRLab Science website](#), while the relevant design papers are Schlawin et al. (2014 — Blanco version) and Herter et al. (2020 — SOAR modifications and performance). It has been in regular use since the 2019A semester.
- We are upgrading the Blanco **IR imager (ISPI)** and moving it to SOAR rather than attempt a major upgrade of Spartan. The Spartan IR imager is nearing the end of its useful lifetime, as its detectors and electronics are deteriorating and cannot easily be repaired. The ISPI upgrade was determined to present lower technical risk and cost. The new capability will offer a similar field of view to Spartan (approximately 5x5 arcmin) but with a single monolithic array and pixels better matched to SOAR image quality. ISPI will continue to provide a set of narrowband and broadband filters covering the near-infrared from Y through K bands. Work on the upgrade is underway, and it will likely be commissioned soon after STELES.

The **Goodman High-Throughput Spectrograph** was delivered in 2004 and saw regular science use starting in semester 2008A, at which time it quickly became the most-used instrument on the telescope. Since then, it has seen several upgrades aimed at improving its efficiency and reliability, including addition of a second, red-sensitive camera as an alternative to the original blue camera (2016B) and provision of a dedicated target acquisition camera (2015B).

Telescope Systems

The telescope itself has not been neglected, and a series of projects have been underway since 2014. Of these, the most significant are the following:

- Upgrades to the original telescope control system (TCS). The original SOAR TCS (Schumacher et al. 2004) has an architecture that is shared with the Blanco and (to a large extent) Rubin telescopes. Improvements implemented for Blanco as part of DECam installation (Warner et al. 2012) were subsequently applied to SOAR, starting in 2014 and completing in 2016.

- Upgrades to the telescope mount control and power drive units (MCU and PDU). This project started in late 2017 and is largely complete as of late 2023 (initial concept in Cancino et al. 2018). This project can be thought of as the “next layer down” from the TCS. It involved replacing original obsolescent proprietary hardware and software with modern hardware and software. The new system is also generally compatible with other NOIRLab telescopes. Furthermore, better telemetry provides better diagnostics of failures, which means recovery can be quicker. The figure shows an example of the mount performance with the upgraded system.
- Upgrades to the telescope active optics controls. Two subsystems have been upgraded:
 - ▷ The control system for the primary mirror actuators has been upgraded to provide faster response times, which allow telescope slews in elevation to complete more rapidly. This work was completed in 2018.
 - ▷ The calibration wavefront sensor (CWFS), which is used for tuning the active optics at the start of every night, replaced obsolete cameras and a lenslet array (David et al. 2020). This work was completed in 2021 (working under pandemic conditions).
- Wavefront-sensing guiders. The original guiders provided only guiding (including fast guiding driving the tip-tilt function of the tertiary mirror). This meant that changes in telescope focus during the night required pausing to determine a new focus setting. Additionally, experience with the active optics showed that residual astigmatism could develop during the night. The only solution in this case was to re-tune the optics using the calibration wavefront sensor. After several experimental investigations, a design was developed that would support guiding, auto-focus, and astigmatism correction, using a 2x2 Shack-Hartmann sensor (Tokovinin et al. 2018). The new design also had to fit within the existing instrument support structures at both the optical and IR Nasmyth foci. The guiders are similar but not identical, because the internal layout at each focus is different. The guider for the optical Nasmyth was installed in July 2022 and fully commissioned during subsequent months. The guider for the IR Nasmyth was installed in September 2023, and commissioning of all functions is underway. In both cases basic guiding was implemented as part of the initial installation. Both guiders use modern EM-CCD cameras, as the devices on the original guiders are no longer supported.

Observing Modes

SOAR was intended to provide a robust remote observing capability, in particular because the two university partners (Michigan State University and University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill) wanted to use the telescope for training students and early-career staff. Additionally, the SOAR design allowed rapid switching between instruments — a few minutes at most.

Ease of access and flexibility meant that SOAR could support programs that required frequent observations — for example, monitoring of supernovae or near-Earth objects on a monthly time scale. This approach is satisfactory for large programs, which can use full nights on a monthly cadence. It was recognized that this type of classical scheduling was not ideal for smaller programs or those requiring more frequent observations. SOAR does support target of opportunity programs, but it is not practical to support too many of them, because the impact on standard observing programs would be too severe.

Queue observing was an obvious solution, but SOAR needed it to be cost-effective; queue observing can be labor-intensive and too expensive for a small facility. The solution was to implement a highly automated queue as part of the Astronomical Event Observatory Network (AEON), in collaboration with the Las Cumbres Observatory (Street et al. 2020; see also Elias and Briceño 2020). In its present form, the AEON queue supports the two most-used

instruments at SOAR (Goodman HTS and TripleSpec 4.1); somewhat more than 20% of the observing time is scheduled in this mode, providing a weekly cadence or better. At present, most of the AEON time is NOIRLab time, with some additional Chilean time.

Acknowledgments

This work is the result of efforts by many engineering and scientific staff, primarily in Chile but also at SOAR partner institutions. Without their hard work over the last decade, SOAR would not be the productive facility that it is today.

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